

Emotional Intelligence as a Determinant of Bullying Behaviour of Adolescents in Police Barracks in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated Emotional Intelligence as determinants of bullying behaviour of adolescents in police barracks in Rivers State, Nigeria. A correlational design was used in this study. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of this study comprised all adolescents living in Police Barracks in Rivers State. The sample was 200 respondents sampled from three Police Area Commands in Rivers State namely; Port Harcourt Area Command, Ahoada Area Command and Bori Area Command. The study used two instruments adopted from various authors, namely Bullying Behaviour Scale and Emotional Intelligence Scale to collect data. The content and face validation of the Instruments was determined by five specialists two from measurement and evaluation and three from educational psychology. A 26 item questionnaire on emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour was administered to respondents. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The result obtained showed that a weak and negative relationship existed among emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in Police Barrack in Rivers State. It was recommended that emotional intelligence training should be included in the orientation programme of adolescents living in Police Barracks. This is to enable them develop the necessary life skills for optimal functioning not only in Police Barracks but also in other future purposes.

Keywords: *Intimidation, Abuse, Provocation, Victim, Bullying*

Introduction

There is need for awareness of the complex nature of bullying behaviour and the extent to which it affects Nigerian adolescents especially those living in police barracks. Themes in classic literature and memories of adolescent students all over the world attest to the common presence of intimidation, threat, abuse and bullying of student by other peers. Thus, a single adolescent who bullied in the school and immediate environment creates a climate of fear and

intimidation to victims and fellow peers as well in the society. Adolescents exposed to bullying are much more likely to experience deteriorated self-esteem suffer from isolation and become fearful and avoidant after being victimized. It is actually a behavioural pattern that deviates from certain rules or laws enacted by constituted authorities and also contrary to the societal norms and moral standards. It is a form of aggressive behaviour that is characterized by deliberate, repeated show of power (Tsang, Hui & Law, 2011).

Kokkimos and Kiprits (2012) see bullying as unprovoked, intentional and repetitive act which displays an imbalance of power that aims to cause physical or psychological harm. Bullying includes a range of behaviour that results in an imbalance of power between the aggressor and the victim. Such behaviour includes not only physical aggression but also verbal harassment and public humiliation, for example, name calling and spreading rumors (Thompson & Sharp, 2013).

Bullying can lead to negative outcomes for both the bully and the victim because adolescent who participate in bullying are at risk of lacking compassion and concern for others by becoming desensitized to bullying which becomes part of their normal daily life. They are at an increased risk for dropping out of school and failing academically which can lead to involvement in gangs and participating in delinquent and anti-social behavior. In later life, they might have difficulty sustaining healthy intimate relationship and can become abusive spouses and parents. This can lead to a higher risk of depression and suicide (Tsang, Hui & Law, 2011).

Agulanna (2014) opined that long term exposure to bullying may also have consequences for the victim's livelihood through absenteeism and even ruin a career. Bullied children may experience headaches, sleeplessness, anxiety, depression and psychosomatic complaints (Sourander, Klomek, Ikonen, Lindroos, Huntamo, Koskelainen & Helen in Agulanna, 2014). These circumstances if not checked could negatively affect educational and social development of the young persons.

Numerous programmes have been created for bullying prevention and safety of adolescents. Research suggests that in order for intervention programmes to be effective, they must be long term (Schutte, et al, 2008) and part of a comprehensive school counselling programmes (Limber, 2002). However, many of these preventive strategies which include focusing on the social environment of the school, assessing bullying at yours school, gathering staff and parent support for bullying prevention, form a group to coordinate the schools bullying prevention activities, increasing adult supervision in hot spots where bullying occurs, intervening consistently and appropriately bullying situation, train your staff in bullying prevention and establishing and enforcing school rules and policies related to bullying (Health Resources and Services Administration, 2014) Although many of these strategies to prevent school violence could be utilized, the effectiveness of a violence prevention program depends on the quality of implementation of the intervention as much as the type of intervention selected (Hermann & Finn, 2002). To this end, it is noted that an effective intervention should take into consideration major correlates and determinants of the problem.

Despite the numerous interventions bullying still persist in police barracks in Rivers State. The extent to which bulling is influenced by factors as emotional intelligence have not been given

much priority in research. For instance, emotions are primary sources of human energy, aspiration and drive activating their innermost feeling and purpose in life and transforming them from things we think about to values we live. The key factor is the way that we interpret our circumstances, based on our prior experiences and belief system, to either respond reactively like a stimulus response machine with an emotion that is outside our control may be inappropriate and self defeating or to respond proactively with self determined responsibility and freedom of choice (George, 2000).

Hence, emotional intelligence plays an integral role in defining character and determining both their individual and group destinies. It involves the ability to monitor among them and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions (Goleman in Ayodele and Sotonade, 2014). Goleman further defined emotional intelligence as the capacity of creating positive outcomes in relationships with others and oneself, as well as adequate relationship with the immediate environment which will promote peaceful co-existence among significant others. Mayer and Salovey cited in Ayodele and Sotonade (2014) see emotional intelligence as the ability to monitor one's own and other feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and use this information to guide ones thinking and actions. Therefore, emotional intelligence training is one of the major skills needed by individual, especially adolescents for self-control, self-awareness, cooperation and empathy that are necessary for sound decision-making. Smith (2007) asserts that such a skill is critical to making the right choices and in molding the adolescent's brain for making strong emotional responses to meet daily life challenges. According to Stein, (2009) emotional intelligence creates self-awareness among adolescents, which is the ability to understand ones emotions and feelings. It enables an individual to tune into and evaluate his or her true feelings. An understanding of one's true feelings, grants the individual the power to manage his or her emotions. Emotional intelligence has been seen as the capacity of creating positive outcomes in relationship with others and oneself, as well as adequate relationship with immediate environment which will promote peaceful coexistence among significant others. It is the thinking of the researcher that there may be a relationship between the emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents.

Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity (Haiger, in Onuigbo, 2012). Depending on the context, the term may refer to biological sex (i.e the state of being male, female or intersex), sex based social structure (including gender roles and other social roles) or gender identity. To Okeke (2013), gender refers to the socially and culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in any society. Gender is a major factor that determines the level of bullying behaviour of adolescents in the society. Okeke, further described the male's attribute as bold, aggressive, tactful and economical on the use of words, while the females are fearful, timid, gentle, dull, submissive and talkative. That may be the reason Salmivalli, (2010), Salmivali, and Voeten (2004), stated that boys are more actively involved in bullying process and are more likely to acquire the participant roles of the reinforcers and the assistants in bullying situations whereas girls are more likely to participate in the roles of the defender and the passive bystanders in bullying situations. Girls are nominated as defenders

more often than boys both by their classmates and victims. Thus in today's society boys are brought up to be aggressive and are involved in tough and tumble play while girls are brought up to be sensitive and caring and to behave in more pro-social and helping ways (Salmivalli, Lagerspratz, Bjorkqvist, Osterman & Kukiaine, 1996).

Despite the effort of schools, parents, psychologists, government and non-governmental organizations to prevent or stop bullying, it still occurs worldwide and is common in Police Barracks. The most prevalence of bullying in the police barrack include name calling, put-downs, insults, harassment, assault, threats, coercion and extortion use among others. Barhight, Hubbahg and Hyde (2013) states that victims of frequent bullying have been reported to experience a range of psychological, psychosomatic and behavioural symptoms including anxiety and insecurity, low self esteem and low self –efficacy, low self-worth, considerable mental health problem, sleeping difficulties, bed wetting, feeling of sadness and frequent headaches and pains. Bullying thus is likely to evoke a range of ideas and situation in different people's minds. Some of these common behaviours are hitting, kicking, extortion of money. Others are likely to be less common, for instance, children and adolescents who bully thrive on controlling or dominating others. They have often been the victims of physical abuse or bullying themselves. Bullies may also be depressed, angry or upset about event at school or at home. In essence, bullying behaviour is a compulsive need to displace aggression which is achieved by the expression of inadequacy (social, personal, interpersonal, behavioural, professional) by projection of that inadequacy onto others through control and subjugation (criticism, exclusion, isolation) (Albiero, Benetle & Altoe, 2007). This is sustained by abdication of responsibility (denial, counter accusation, pretences of victimhood) and perpetuated by a climate of fear, ignorance, indifference, silence, denial, disbelief, deception, evasion of accountability, tolerance and reward (promotion) for the bully and victim (Thomberg & Jungert, 2013). Though a number of studies by Abbitt in Agulanna (2014), and Rigby (2014) and Wang, Iannotti, Nansel (2009) on school bullying among adolescents, seminars, symposia as well as rallies have been done before now, a lot still needs to be done to create awareness and check the menace of bullying behaviour in their society and also educate adolescents on the causes, effects, predictors and consequences of bullying, both in relation to being a bully and being a victim of bullying behaviour on mental health and academic performance. Hence, this study is to examine emotional intelligence as a determinant of bullying behaviour of adolescents in police barracks in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Bullying is a social phenomenon that is a major problem in today's society, and studies have shown that children exposed to bullying are much more likely to experience long-term as well as immediate negative psychological impacts. Persistent bullying may lower victims self-confidence, induce serious health problems and ruin careers. More bullied children may suffer headache, sleeplessness, anxiety, depression and psychosomatic complaint. Some of the bullied children equally develop post-traumatic stress disorder, unheard victims may turn to inward violence, suicide or outward violence. Bullies are described as anxious, lead to academically uneducated and insecure and tend to be aggressive and coercive. They display negative attitude

towards their peers and tend to solve their problems with violence. Youth violence in the barracks is also seen as more likely to involve weapons and gangs, to be more destructive and to involve adolescents than ever before. While there is a lack of strong evidence to support an actual increase in the prevalence and severity of adolescents bullying behaviour, there is, nonetheless a growing sense of complex social issue. Clearly, bullying behaviour among adolescents is an issue that needs to be examined, understood and ameliorated through effective, concerted and sustained efforts. The understanding of the functioning of emotional intelligence in the occurrence of bullying behaviour could provide for better development of a lasting and effective intervention. It is towards this end that this study was designed to examine emotional intelligence as a determinant of bullying behaviour of adolescents in police barracks in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate emotional intelligence as determinants of bullying behaviour of adolescents

Specifically, the researcher sought to determine:

- (i) The relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.
- (ii) If gender is a factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- (i) What is the relationship between emotional intelligence, and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks?
- (ii) To what extent is gender a factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying Behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study:

- (i) There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.
- (ii) Gender is not a significant factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.

Method

The research design adopted for the study is correlational design. According to Nworgu (2015), a correlation research design seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. The area of the study was Rivers State, the population of this study was 2573 adolescents from the various Police barracks in the three Area Command in Rivers State. The study adopted a cluster sampling technique in which three Area Command in Rivers State

namely; Port Harcourt Area Command, Bori Area Command and Ahoada Area Command. A sample size of 200 adolescents from the population of the study was selected for the study.

The researcher used two instruments for the study. They are Bullying Behaviour Scale (BBS), and Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS). The first instrument Bullying Behaviour Scale (BBS) was adopted from Buluch, Fulbright and Williams (2003) to elicit information on bullying behaviour, while Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) was adopted from Low and Drawn (2000) to elicit information on Emotional Intelligence. The instrument were made-up of two sections A&B. Section A was based on Bullying Behaviour Scale (BBS) which has 14 items, while Section B was based on the Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) with 12 items instruments. The response was categorized into 4 points rating scale of Exactly true, Moderately true, Barely true and Not of all true respectively.

The reliability of the first instrument “Bullying Behaviour Scale” (BBS) was obtained using a Cronbach Alpha for bullying behaviour scale with a coefficient of 0.82 obtained while the second part of the instrument “Emotional Intelligence Scale” (EIS) was obtained using split half for internal consistency with the coefficient of 0.79.

The researcher employed direct delivery method in the administration of the instruments to the research subject. This implies that the researcher administered the instruments personally to the respondents with the help of two (2) trained research assistants from the Police barracks, one for each cluster and the two hundred were found to have been correctly filled and fit for use in further analysis. That data were collated to obtain mean and standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients.

The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Hypotheses 1 and 2 was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient These were done with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Mean score of 2.5 was the benchmark. Hence, any item with mean score of 2.5 and above was considered positive and accepted as being significant, while items with mean scores of 2.49 below were considered negative and insignificant.

Results

Research Question One: What is the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barrack.

Table 1: Pearson product moment Correlation on Emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in Police Barracks.

Variables	n	\bar{x}	SD	r
Emotional Intelligence (EI)	200	33.082	2.702	-0.106
Bullying Behaviour (BB)	200	32.160	2.800	

n= number of Subjects, \bar{x} = Mean. SD = standard deviation, r = Reliability coefficient.

Table 1 shows the r value calculated as -0.106 indicating that the relationship between Emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour is negatively weak. Also the mean and standard deviation of the two variables, emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of

adolescents living in police barracks, Emotional intelligence (EI) has the highest mean ($\bar{x}=33.082$) followed by bullying behaviour (BB) the lowest mean ($\bar{x}=32.160$).

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in Police Barrack.

Table 2: Correlations matrix showing relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barrack.

Variables	E. I.	B. B
Emotional Intelligence (EI)	1.000	
Bullying Behaviour (BB)	-0.106	1.000

Table 2 shows the correlations between Emotional Intelligence and bullying behaviour is -0.106 indicates a very weak negative relationship of adolescents living in Police Barrack.

Research Question Two: To what extent is gender a factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.

Table 3: Pearson product moment on gender as a factor in the emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in Police barracks.

Variables	n	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	r	Emotional intelligence of
Males	100	33.311	2.835	-.023	
Emotional intelligence of Females	100	33.033	2.737		

n= Number of subjects, \bar{x} = Mean, SD= standard deviation, r= reliability coefficient.

The result from table 3 revealed that there is significant weak negative relationship between gender as a factor in emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents. ($r = -.023$). Emotional intelligence of male adolescent group mean is 33.311 with standard deviation of 2.835 while that of emotional intelligence of female adolescents group is 33.033 with standard deviation of 2.737. The mean scores are almost equal.

Hypothesis Two: Gender is not a significant factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.

Table 4: Correlations between gender as a factor in the emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks.

Variables	Emotional Intelligence of Males	Emotional Intelligence of Females
Emotional Intelligence of Males	1	-.023
Emotional Intelligence of Females	-.023	1

Correlation is not significant at 0.05 (2-tailed), $n = 90$.

Pearson Product Moment Correlations Coefficient was calculated in table 11 for a relationship between Emotional intelligence of males and females adolescent living in Police barracks. A negative weak correlation was found $r(88) = -.023, P > 0.05$ indicating no significant linear relationship between the two variables.

Discussion of Findings

The result obtained from Research Question One and Hypothesis One revealed the relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour of adolescents living in police barracks. The results indicated that a weak negative relationship exist between emotional intelligence and bullying behaviour which was confirmed in the study, attention must be invested in helping the adolescents in barrack build pro-social behaviour that will be devoid of any form of aggression, violence, bullying behavior and so on. For instance, studies conducted by Femandez-Berrocal, Salovey, Vera, Extremera, Ramos, (2005) shows that individual who pay lesser attention to their own emotions, individuals who score lower on emotional clarity, and individual who report an inability to regulate their own emotional states show poor emotional adjustment on a number of measures and increased tendency for bullying. Conversely, individuals reporting greater emotional clarity and a greater ability to repair their own emotional states report higher levels of self-esteem, another important indicator of mental health and emotional intelligence (Salmon, James, Smith 1998). Indeed, adolescents who are able to perceive, handle, understand and express their emotions tend to be more socially accepted by their peer group and experience better interpersonal relationships (Austin, Sakiofske & Egan, 2005). As Petrides et al (2004) point out, students with adequate social and emotional skills are less likely to experience and externalize distress through anti-social behaviour, while those with poor social and emotional skills are more likely to feel excluded which may lead to anti-social behaviour.

The computed outcome of the two research question and hypothesis was found to be statistically insignificant. This evidently shows that there is no relationship between emotional intelligence of male and female adolescents living in police barracks. The findings reported in the current study; do not support previous research findings of Siann, Lockhart and Rawson (2008). They found that boys may be more likely to be perpetrators and victims of bullying behaviour than girls.

However, boys tend to be more actively involved in bullying behaviour than girls. Salmivalli & Isaac (2005) argue that this finding is attributed to boys tendency to use more physically aggressive ways of interacting, because such behaviour is more socially approved by the peer group of boys than of girls. However, in the case of indirect bullying, the finding that boys use more indirect forms of bullying is inconsistent with many previous studies.

The reasons for the differences in the findings could be attributed to the fact that most of the studies on bullying behaviour were carried out mainly on boys (males). Secondly it may be that life in police barracks is quite different from those outside the barracks setting and also it may be deduced that the occupational or vocational life styles of parents or guardians of those living in police barracks might have effects on the adolescents' behavior (i.e bullying behaviour).

Conclusion

The study investigated the emotional intelligence as determinants of bullying behaviour of adolescents in police barracks in Rivers State. Bullying is a social phenomenon that is a major problem in today's society, and studies have shown that children exposed to bullying are much more likely to experience long-term as well as immediate negative psychological impacts. The impacts of emotional intelligence training will develop a necessary life skill for optimal functioning of adolescents in police barrack. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the emotional intelligence as determinants of bullying behaviour of adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Psychologists and guidance counselors should enlightened parents and adolescents on the best ways to live a healthy life which is devoid of violence on police barracks in order to promote good mental health.
- 2) Non-governmental organizations should organize rallies and symposia programmes of letting them to know that negative effects of bullying behaviour on adolescents themselves for example, parents, family, and peers.

Consequently, professional helpers such as counselors, health workers among others who are serving in the police and living in the barracks should be saddled with responsibilities of providing guidance and counseling services and disseminating information that will help reduce the incidence of bullying behaviour among adolescents in police barracks.

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